

Awareness and Utilization of Web 2.0 Technology for Learning among Science Teacher Trainees in Akwa Ibom State

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Abstract

This study examined assessment on awareness and utilization of Web 2.0 technologies among science teacher trainees in Akwa Ibom State University. Three research questions and two hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. Survey research design was adopted, the Population of the study consists of 387 (187 male and 200 female) science teacher trainees during the 2022/2023 academic session in Akwa Ibom State. 120 (52 male and 68 Female) science teacher trainees constitute the sample size of the study, this was arrived at using simple random sampling technique. A structured questionnaire tagged Science Teacher Trainees' Awareness and Utilization of Web 2.0 Technology (STTAUWT) was used for data collection and was validated by two experts. 30 respondents which were not part of the study were used to obtain reliability index of 0.75 using Cronbach's Alpha. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics to answer the questions while the independent t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The results revealed among others that there was no significant difference in the opinions of male and female science teacher trainees on their awareness and utilization of Web 2.0 technology in Akwa Ibom State University. It was concluded that Web 2.0 technology provide a level user interaction and offered free services, sites for immediate feedback. It was recommended among others that Web 2.0 technology should be used for teaching and learning in order to create opportunities for teacher trainees to learn and develop at their own pace in e-learning environment.

Keywords: Awareness. Utilization, technology and teachers' trainees

Introduction

The introduction of Web 2.0 technologies is an innovative method of disseminating knowledge and also serves as a powerful tool for the acquisition of skills. Communication skills for instance, are very important in teaching and learning processes (Babayemi & Utibe, 2017). Complete integration of technologies in teaching learning process enhances effective communication, lifelong and life-wide learning. Web 2.0 technology usage in learning process empower student to interact with others and access abundance resources. It provides immediate feedback and encourages self-directed learning to students. In this 21st century Web technologies when effectively used with others instructional materials make teaching and learning easy. In fact, the use of international networking allows for global transfer of data from one computer to another and allows free flow of communication and information for researches or assignment.

The term Web 2.0 is used to describe Web applications that are designed to be user centered and to aid the interaction of information sharing and collaboration on the World Wide Web which has created the social media platforms that are highly interactive. According to Yun-Jo and William cited by Ughelu (2016), Web 2.0 is a social revolution that makes it possible for people to participate through open application and services. Social medial sites and social networking are examples of Web 2.0 technologies amongst which is the dropbox and skype application. Wordu and Itighise (2020) comments that dropbox cloud-based applications is significantly critical to the progress and future of education serve as a way of transforming teaching-learning process and enhances students' academic performance when compared to expository methods. Itighise and Akpan (2021) comments that cloud computing technologies allow users to alter the content of web pages and interact with others.

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Web 2.0 technologies as a dynamic internet application that allows users to communicate with each other by creating, editing and sharing information. These technologies typically include Blogs, Forums, Wikis, Micro-messaging, Cloud computing, social Networking tools, Multimedia sharing, Social book-marking and podcast etc. The Web 2.0 technologies is different from the earlier Web 1.0 which is characterized as "read only Web".

According to Nazzal (2018) Web 2.0 technology is a "read-write Web" which are suitable for active and meaningful learning and information sharing, communication, collaborations and learning management. It provides users with room for interactivity that enhance the creation and sharing of information. Olannye, Nwaodume and Okegbe (2020) revealed that over 90% of students responded that they used social networking service such as Facebook, My space, Skype and LinkedIn in teaching and learning process. Technology usage in educational system have the potential to innovate, accelerate, enrich, deepen skills, motivate and engage students, relate school experience to work practices, create economic viability for tomorrow's workers, as well as strengthening teaching. Traditionally, teaching is viewed as a process of delivery to students what is required and without any opportunity for questioning. This means that the teacher has the Monopoly of knowledge required to be imparted. However, in the modern sense, teaching is an attempt to help learner acquire change of attitude, knowledge, idea, skill or application.

The features of Web 2.0 technologies are capable of helping students in their learning process. In the learning of science, the process involves doing, that is, hands-on. To help students learn and do science, they can use technology. Students can video laboratory processes like dissections and any form of practical work to be watched later as well as pictures can be taken and shared. Yan cited by Abudulkadir (2019) posits that students constantly use Web 2.0 technology for their daily communication and to access information for their personal use as they send Instant Message to friends and colleagues take pictures and post them online. Students share information, video, audio, chat and network with the people they met online which help in increasing learners' satisfaction with a course, improving their learning and writing ability and increasing students-students interaction.

Itighise and Thomas (2022) posits that teacher trainees use Web 2.0 tools for publishing their personal view, network with other students and promote student-centered interaction. According to Nazzal (2018), lecturers still adhere to the teaching method that stands them out as dispensers of knowledge rather than facilitators which is associated with chalk and talk method of teaching with the learning environment being teacher/lecturer centred. Tim (2016) comments that Web 2.0 websites enable users to create, share, collaborate and communicate their work with others, without any need of any web design or publishing skills. Generally, Web 2.0 technologies provide immediate feedback and dynamic internet applications that allows users to communicate with each other by creating, editing and sharing information. Anderson cited by Yin and Tsai (2021) indicate that there has been a growing trend of incorporating technology in education to fulfill some of the technological expectations of students. Evidently, emerging technologies such as Web 2.0 technologies have been adopted and integrate to foster teaching and learning activities in universities and colleges.

This study focused on Socio-constructivist theory propounded by Lev Vygotsky, a Russian teacher and psychologist in 1978. Lev Vygotsky state that people learn through their interactions, communications with others and how social environments influence the learning process. He proposed that learning takes place through the interactions students have with their peers, teachers, and other experts. Consequently, teachers can create a learning environment that maximizes the learner's ability to interact with each other through discussion, collaboration and feedback. Moreover, Vygotsky (1978) argues that culture and collaboration is the primary determining factor for knowledge construction. Vygotsky believed that knowledge is not only personally constructed but that it is also socially mediated. By this, he implied that although individuals have to construct their own meaning of a phenomena or idea, the process of constructing meaning is always embedded within the social setting of which the individual is part. Hence, social constructivists view learning as an active process where learners should learn to discover principles, concepts and facts for themselves through collaboration which encourage group work and intuitive thinking. The implication of this theory to the present study is that, the theory emphasizes the idea that learners make sense of their experiences by constructing their own understanding through their own "mental models" and by sharing of ideas among students. Utilization of Web 2.0 technology such as WhatsApp, Skype, Dropbox, IMOchat etc allow interaction between student-student and student-teachers in the classroom to accommodate new experiences.

Empirically, this study is in line with the earlier studies by Itighise and Akpan (2021) examined Educators utilization of ICT facilities for mastery learning in post COVID -19 era in selected state universities in South South, Nigeria. The population of the study was derived from 2019/2020 academic session which comprised of 225 science educators. A total of 105 were selected using simple random sampling techniques. Data were gathered using questionnaire titled assessment of science educators' access and utilization of information and communication technology (ICT) for mastery teaching and

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learning". The questionnaire contained two sections: science educator access to ICT facilities and science Educators utilization of ICT facilities for mastering teaching and learning in post COVID-19 era. The reliability indices of the cluster A and B of the instrument were estimated to 0.89 and 0.78 using Cronbach's alpha method. The data collected were analyzed using percentages, mean and standard deviation to answer the two research questions. The result revealed that 52.50% of science educators access ICT facilities at home and 50.40% at their personal offices. The study also show that the mean score science educators utilization of ICT facilities for mastery teaching and learning in the post COVID-19 era are more 2.50 criterions mean. It was concluded from the study that all education activities in Nigeria should be geared toward ICT oriented to avoid closure of schools as in the case of COVID-19 pandemic. It was therefore recommended among other that government of Nigeria should direct political powers toward improving our education system through full blown ICT utilization in teaching learning process for promotion of mastery teaching in academic institutions. It is against this background the study assessed science teacher trainees' awareness and utilization of Web 2.0 technology in Akwa Ibom State.

It is a common knowledge that the utilization of the internet has made the world a global village. Experience are shared, knowledge are acquired, information transmitted via the Internet. The ability of a student to utilize the internet effectively is a significant advantage on their side. In Akwa Ibom State University, there is a provision of free internet connectivity for every staff and the entire department of Science Education have resource center with internet connectivity and computer analyst. The high level of low scores among science teacher trainees in universities has been traced to traditional teaching methods that promote activities of teachers and passiveness of learners who perceive the learning content with just the auditory mode assuring very poor retention an recall of contents.

However, web 2.0 technology as a social media platform has been developed to be an effective virtual communication medium through a computing platform that reside in a service provider's large data center which is able to dynamically provide sever's ability to address a wider range of needs of their clients or learners. This technology provides opportunities for supporting and enhancing teaching and learning strategies and practices. The question is: What is the level of science teacher trainees' awareness of the web 2.0 technologies in learning process? Do science teacher trainees' make use of the web 2.0 technologies available online for effective learning process? The study therefore assessed science teacher trainees' awareness and utilization of Web 2.0 technology in Akwa Ibom State.

Objectives of the study

The aim of this study is to assess level of awareness and utilization of Web 2.0 technologies for learning process among science teacher trainee in Akwa Ibom State. Specifically, the objectives of the study are to:

1. Determine the level of science teacher trainee's awareness on Web 2.0 technology tools for learning in Akwa Ibom State.
2. Assess the level of science teacher trainees' utilization of Web 2.0 technology tools for learning in Akwa Ibom State.
3. Determine the level of awareness on Web 2.0 technology tools for learning among male and female science teacher trainees in Akwa Ibom State.
4. Determine the level of utilization of Web 2.0 technology tools for learning among male and female science teacher trainees in Akwa Ibom State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study.

1. What is the level of science teacher trainees' awareness on Web 2.0 technology tools for learning in Akwa Ibom State?
2. What is the level of science teacher trainees' utilization of Web 2.0 technology tools for learning in Akwa Ibom State?
3. What is the level of awareness on Web 2.0 technology tools for learning among male and female science teacher trainees in Akwa Ibom State?
4. What is the level of utilization of Web 2.0 technology tools for learning among male and female science teacher trainees in Akwa Ibom State?

Hypotheses:

Base on the research questions two null hypotheses was formulated.

There is no significant difference between mean score of respondents on level of awareness of web 2.0 technologies for learning among male and female science teacher trainees in Akwa Ibom State

Methodology

The design adopted for this study is the survey research design. The Population of the study consists of 387 (187 male & 200 female) science teacher trainees during the 2022/2023 academic session in Akwa Ibom State. 120 (52 male & 68 Female)

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science teacher trainees constitute the sample size of the study, this was arrived at using simple random sampling technique. The instrument for Data collection was research-made structured questionnaire, tagged Science Teacher Trainees Awareness and Utilization of Web 2.0 Technology Questionnaire (STTAUWTQ), which is made up of 40 items. The 30 items in questionnaire covered the level of awareness and utilization of Web 2.0 technology which was developed on a four point rating scale. The questionnaire had three Sections A, B and C which corresponded to the research questions. For research question one and two rating scale was as follow. Very High Level (VHL) - 4 points; High Level (HL) - 3 points; Low Level (LL) - 2 points; Very Low Level (VLL) -1point. In order to ensure content and face validity of the instruments, draft copies were given to two lecturers for face and content validation from the Department of science Education, Faculty of Education, Akwa Ibom state University. All comments and corrections were reflected in the final form of the instruments. The instrument was administered personally by the researcher to 30 respondents which were not part of the sample size and the data obtained were analyzed using Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient package using SPSS 17. The reliability coefficient of 0.75 was obtained. This coefficient shows that the instrument was reliable for the study. All the copies administered were returned with valid responses. The data generated from the retrieved instrument were analyzed using descriptive statistics to answer the research questions, while the independent t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the level of science teacher trainees' awareness on Web 2.0 technology tools for learning in Akwa Ibom State?

Table 1: Frequency Counts, Mean and Standard Deviation on Level of Science Teacher Trainee's Awareness of Web 2.0 Technology Tools For Learning Process in Akwa Ibom State. (N=120)

S/N	Items	VHL	HL	LL	VLL	Mean	Std. Dev.
1.	I am aware that IMO Web 2.0 allows learners to visually share lesson content through short compressed video or live experience video	59	36	13	13	3.18	1.00
2	I am aware that Facebook is free collaborative tool that provides anxiety free environment for learning	62	42	11	5	3.34	0.81
3	I am aware that Dropbox application is a fascinating, file hosting service that facilitates transactional learning	28	63	19	10	2.91	0.85
4	I am aware that Skype can be used to share video lesson content	32	51	25	12	2.86	0.93
5	I do not have knowledge of the potential of using WhatsApp in teaching and learning process	30	57	16	17	2.83	0.96
6	I do not have sufficient knowledge of effective application of Instagram as web 2.0 teaching and learning tools	27	56	23	14	2.80	0.92
7	I do not have knowledge of the potential of using Google Talk in teaching and learning process	25	58	21	16	2.77	0.93
8	I do not have knowledge of the potential of using My Space in the teaching and learning process	26	55	21	18	2.74	0.97
9	I am aware that Twitter can be used to share lesson content	61	31	15	13	3.17	1.02
10	I am aware that Blogs can be used to share video lesson content	58	26	20	16	3.05	1.09
11	I am aware of effective utilization of Email in teaching and learning process	52	29	21	18	2.96	1.10
12	I do not have knowledge of the potential of using Wiki in teaching and learning process	69	39	7	5	3.43	0.79
13	I do not have knowledge of the potential of using LinkedIn in learning process	17	25	47	31	2.23	0.99
14	I do not have knowledge of the potential of using Flickr in teaching and learning process	25	41	39	15	2.63	0.95
15	I am aware that YouTube can be used to share lesson content	71	37	9	3	3.47	0.74
	Grand Mean					2.96	0.94

Table 1 shows the frequency counts, mean and standard deviation on the level of science teacher trainee's awareness of Web 2.0 technology tools for learning process in Akwa Ibom State University. The result shows that the grand mean of

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respondents over the level of science teacher trainee’s awareness of Web 2.0 technology tools for learning process in Akwa Ibom State University was 2.96 and standard deviation of 0.94. Participants responded most positively to the item that stated “I am aware that YouTube can be used to share lesson content” (M = 3.47, SD = 0.74), this was followed by “I do not have knowledge of the potential of using Wiki in teaching and learning process” (M = 3.43, SD = 0.79). The participant also responded high to the item that stated that “I am aware that Facebook is free collaborative tool that provide anxiety free environment for learning” (M= 3.34, SD=0.81), and the least positive to the item that stated “I do not have knowledge of the potential of using LinkedIn in learning process” (M= 2.23, SD= 0.99). The mean scores for all items were high and since the grand mean is greater than 2.5, the result shows that there is a high of level of science teacher trainee’s awareness of Web 2.0 technology tools for learning process in Akwa Ibom State University.

Research Question 2

What is the level of science teacher trainee’s utilization of Web 2.0 technology tools for learning process in Akwa Ibom State?

Table 2: Frequency Counts, Mean and Standard Deviation on Level of Science Teacher Trainee’s Utilization of Web 2.0 Technology Tools For Learning Process In Akwa Ibom State

S/N	Items	VHL	HL	LL	VLL	Mean	Std.
1	I do use IMO Web 2.0 to share lesson content learners	7	22	53	38	1.98	0.86
2	I use Facebook as a collaborative tool that provides anxiety free environment for learning	24	47	33	16	2.66	0.95
3	I use Dropbox application as a fascinating file hosting service that facilitates transactional learning delivery	8	25	48	39	2.02	0.90
4	I do not use skype to share video lesson content with my colleagues	58	48	9	5	3.33	0.79
5	I use WhatsApp for teaching and learning process	30	45	26	19	2.72	1.01
6	I like using Instagram as web 2.0 technologies for active and meaningful learning, information sharing and collaboration	12	20	48	40	2.03	0.95
7	I use Google Talk for improving education quality in learning process	12	28	48	32	2.17	0.94
8	I make use of my Space to learn and develop at my own space in e-learning environment	7	19	51	43	1.92	0.87
9	I mostly use Twitter to share lesson content to the learners in order to change their attitude toward knowledge acquisition	3	22	69	26	2.02	0.71
10	I use faculty Blogs to share video lesson content and provides a level user interaction	4	14	53	49	1.78	0.78
11	I use Email for effective teaching and learning process	8	5	80	27	1.95	0.73
12	I make use of Wiki for teaching and learning process	77	34	9	-	3.57	0.63
13	I make use of Flickr for collaboration and sharing of lesson content	42	26	33	19	2.76	1.10

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14	I use LinkedIn in communicating the lesson content to colleagues	16	15	46	43	2.03	1.01
15	I use YouTube to share lesson	24	31	46	19	2.50	0.99
Grand Mean						2.36	0.88

Table 2 shows the frequency counts, mean and standard deviation on the level of science teacher trainee's utilization of Web 2.0 technology tools for learning process in Akwa Ibom State University. The result shows that the grand mean of respondents over the level of science teacher trainee's utilization of Web 2.0 technology tools for learning process in Akwa Ibom State University was 2.36 and standard deviation of 0.88. Participants responded most positively to the item that stated "I make use of Wiki for teaching and learning process" (M = 3.57, SD = 0.63), this was followed by "I do not use skype to share video lesson content with my colleagues" (M = 3.33, SD = 0.79). The participant also responded high to the item that stated that "I do use WhatsApp for teaching and learning process" (M= 2.72, SD= 1.01), and the least response to the item that stated "I do use faculty Blogs to share video lesson content and provides a level user interaction" (M = 1.78, SD= 0.78). Since the grand mean of 2.36 is lesser than 2.5, the result shows that there is a low level of science teacher trainee's utilization of Web 2.0 technology tool for learning process in Akwa Ibom State University.

Research Question 3

What is the level of awareness on Web 2.0 technology tools for learning among male and female science teacher trainees in Akwa Ibom State?

Table 3: Summary of Mean and Standard Deviation on the Level of Awareness of Web 2.0 Technology Tools for Learning Process by Male and Female Science Teacher Trainees

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean diff
Level of Awareness	Male	52	45.04	3.21	1.19
	Female	68	43.85	3.34	

The result in Table 3 shows the level of awareness of Web 2.0 technology for learning process by male and female science teacher trainees. The mean of 45.04 of male respondents was slightly higher than mean of female 43.85 with the mean difference of 1.19 showing slight difference in the level of awareness. To ascertain if the observed mean difference is statistically significant, the data was further subjected to test of analysis using independent t-test statistics. The result is presented in table 5.

Research Question 4

What is the level of utilization of Web 2.0 technology tools for learning among male and female science teacher trainees in Akwa Ibom State?

Table 4: Summary of Mean and Standard Deviation on the Level of Utilization of Web 2.0 Technology Tools for Learning Process by Male and Female Science Teacher Trainees

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean diff
Level of Utilization	Male	52	32.75	4.78	1.12
	Female	68	33.87	3.14	

The result in Table 4 above shows the level of utilization of Web 2.0 technology tools for learning process by male and female science teacher trainees. The result showed that the mean and standard deviation scores (32.75 and 4.78) of male respondents on level of utilization of Web 2.0 technology tools for learning process was slightly lesser than mean and standard deviation scores (33.87 and 3.14) of female respondents. This was observed with a remarkable mean difference of 1.12 showing the difference in the level of utilization of Web 2.0 technology tools for learning process by male and female students in science education. To ascertain if the observed mean difference is statistically significant, the data was further subjected to test of analysis using independent t-test statistics. The result is presented in table 6.

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Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between mean score of respondents on level of awareness of web 2.0 technologies for learning among male and female science teacher trainees in Akwa Ibom State

Table 5: Summary of Independent T-Test on the Difference in the Opinion of Male and Female Science Teacher Trainees on their Level of Awareness of Web 2.0 Technology Tools

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	SD	df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Awareness of Web 2.0	Male	52	45.04	3.21	118	1.95	1.96	Accepted H ₀₁
	Female	68	43.85	3.34				

The result in table 5 revealed that the calculated t-value of 1.95 is lesser than the critical t-value of 1.96 at .05 level of significance and at 118 degrees of freedom. This implies that there is no significant difference in the opinions of male and female science teacher trainees on their level of awareness of Web 2.0 technology tools for learning process. This result shows that the level of awareness of Web 2.0 technology tools for learning process is at the same pace.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between mean score of respondents on utilization of web 2.0 technologies for learning among male and female science teacher trainees in Akwa Ibom State

Table 6: Summary of Independent T-Test on the Difference in the Opinions of Male and Female Science Teacher Trainees on their Level of Utilization of Web 2.0 Technology Tools

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Utilization of Web 2.0	Male	52	32.75	4.78	118	1.54	1.96	Accepted H ₀₂
	Female	68	33.87	3.14				

The result in table 6 revealed that the calculated t-value of 1.54 is lesser than the critical t-value of 1.96 at .05 level of significance and at 118 degrees of freedom. This implies that there is no significant difference between mean score of respondents on utilization of web 2.0 technologies for learning among male and female science teacher trainees in Akwa Ibom State. This result shows that the level of utilization of Web 2.0 technology tools for learning process is at the same pace.

Discussion of Findings

The result of findings in table 5 revealed that the calculated t-value of 1.95 is lesser than the critical t-value of 1.96 at .05 level of significance and at 118 degrees of freedom. This implies that there is no significant difference between mean score of respondents on level of awareness of web 2.0 technologies for learning among male and female science teacher trainees in Akwa Ibom State. Hence, the null hypothesis one of no significant difference is accepted. This result shows that the level of awareness of Web 2.0 technology tools for learning process is at same pace. Web 2.0 technology provide a level user interaction and offered a free service, sites, like Wikipedia and Facebook have grown at amazing fast rates (Berk, 2016). Teacher trainees used Web 2.0 tools for publishing their personal view, network with other students and promote student-centered interaction (Itighise & Thomas,2022).

The result of findings in this hypothesis revealed in table 5 that the calculated t-value of 1.54 is lesser than the critical t-value of 1.96 at .05 level of significance and at 118 degrees of freedom. This implies that there is no significant difference between mean score of respondents on utilization of web 2.0 technologies for learning among male and female science teacher trainees in Akwa Ibom State. Hence, the null hypothesis two of no significant difference is accepted. This result shows that the level of utilization of Web 2.0 technology tools for learning process is at the same pace. Web 2.0 technologies adoption indicates that developing interactive, technology-rich curricula is suitable for preparing students for the present complex world(Mohammad, 2011).

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Conclusion

From the results obtained in the study, technology encourages knowledge-based learning approach and helps to support a student-centered, constructivist, and progressive approach. It was therefore concluded that technology expanded course offerings, and increased students engagement and motivation towards learning. Web 2.0 technologies provide a level user interaction and offered free services, sites like Wikipedia and Facebook, and encourage immediate feedback.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. The findings established a generally low usage of Web 2.0 technologies for teaching and learning process in the university. There is therefore a need for institutional policy on the integration of Web 2.0 technology in teaching and learning activities.
2. The university authorities should consider creating awareness on the different types of Web 2.0 technologies for teaching and learning process and also encourage lecturer used Web 2.0 technologies for communication and collaboration. This would address the issue of non-use and will give students the opportunity to identify and choose the tools that are suitable for specific tasks related to personal, academics or general activities.
3. The university authorities should also put in a place, a programme of user education for students to encourage them and also learn how to use Web 2.0 technology for academic and other purposes
4. Science teacher trainees should be given adequate training through workshop and seminar on how to use Web 2.0 technology for effective learning process.

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